

ISSUES OF ORGANIZATION AND MANAGEMENT OF INCLUSIVE EDUCATION AND UPBRINGING IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: *The process of integration and inclusion of children with disabilities in educational institutions is not only a trend of the new time, but also the realization of children's rights to education. The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Education” guarantees the right of every child to receive knowledge, and the laws “On Guarantees of the Rights of the Child”, “On Preschool Education and Upbringing” provide additional benefits for children with special needs to receive education*

Key words: *Inclusive education, principles of inclusive education, creativity, moral standards, creativity, leading activity, development of the emotional sphere of children.*

Аннотация: *Процесс интеграции и инклюзии детей с ограниченными возможностями в образовательных учреждениях - не только тенденция нового времени, но и реализация прав детей на образование. Закон Республики Узбекистан «Об образовании» гарантирует право каждого ребенка на получение знаний, а законы «О гарантиях прав ребенка», «О дошкольном образовании и воспитании» предусматривают дополнительные льготы на получение образования детьми с особыми потребностями.*

Ключевые слова: *Инклюзивное обучение, принципы инклюзивного обучения, творческие способности, нравственные нормы, способность к творчеству, ведущий вид деятельности, развитие эмоциональной сферы детей.*

The process of integration and inclusion of children with disabilities in educational institutions is not only a trend of the new time, but also the realization of children's rights to education. The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education" guarantees the right of every child to receive knowledge, and the laws "On Guarantees of the Rights of the Child", "On Preschool Education and Upbringing" provide additional benefits for children with special needs to receive education. The topic did not leave the agenda, as there are no fewer children with disabilities. According to the data of the regional department of the Extrabudgetary Pension Fund under the Ministry of Finance of the Republic of Uzbekistan, in the Navoi region, the number of children under 16 with disabilities increased from 4046 to 4419 last year, with a total number of 1214 children aged two to six years. Most of these guys are in Khatyrchi and Kyzyltepa districts. Today, their upbringing and education are carried out on the basis of the state specialized multidisciplinary preschool educational organization No. 16 of the city of Navoi.

As you know, in October 2019, the reorganization of domestic specialized preschool educational institutions and the creation of multidisciplinary institutions on their basis began. This is done with the aim that children with special needs have the opportunity to receive more complete and comprehensive correctional, pedagogical and rehabilitation assistance. Previously, in most specialized children's organizations, such assistance was provided for one type of violation and not in full. Moreover, it did not meet modern requirements. Among the reasons indicated was the outdated material and technical base and the lack of the necessary equipment. Today, assistance is being provided in providing all the necessary specialists at the same time, in equipping the MSDOO with modern equipment, didactic materials, special toys and other accessories that make correctional, pedagogical and rehabilitation procedures as effective as possible. 83 children are currently being brought up in the Navoi multidisciplinary specialized preschool.

These are children not only from Navoi and the nearby Karmana and Navbakhor regions, but also from Kanimekh, Kyzyltepa and even remote Uchkuduk and Nurata. Seven defectologists work with them, the same number of medical

personnel, 20 educators. The condition for organizing successful education and upbringing for such children is the creation of an adaptive environment that excludes any discrimination, provides equal treatment and conditions for providing special educational needs to pupils, an individual approach. And the earlier work with children with disabilities begins, the higher their chances for adaptation and socialization in society, - agrees with the generally accepted principles of organizing the education and upbringing of children with disabilities, the head of the department for ensuring the quality of the educational process and introducing innovative pedagogical technologies for managing preschool education Navoi region Latofat Rajabov. - It should be noted that some skills and abilities that a teacher cannot convey can be explained to a child by a peer: children will understand each other better and faster. Also, the behavior and actions of others have a positive effect on its development. Children brought up in such conditions and environment become more sympathetic, caring.

From experience I can say that the gradual provision of social adaptation of children with disabilities from the age of three in a preschool educational organization has a positive effect. At the stage of social adaptation, the child gets used to strangers, masters the rules of behavior in society, and learns basic skills. At the stage of learning self-service at the level of abilities, it is important through the efforts of teachers and other specialists (psychologist, defectologist) to create conditions for adaptation depending on the individual characteristics of the child and the degree of diagnosis of the disease.

The third stage is to create a friendly and healthy environment in the process of raising children with disabilities in a team with healthy peers, increasing the legal literacy of parents, and ensuring compliance with the provisions of the Convention on the Rights of the Child. We need to introduce inclusive education in general preschool institutions. In specialized preschools, children with disabilities do not adapt to the social environment, they feel isolated from society. When introducing inclusion in preschool education, problems were identified that impede the normal course of the process. Unfortunately, there are many of them. These are insufficient

conditions for the development and rehabilitation of children with various forms of disability, the lack of qualified personnel, as well as cooperation between general organizations and institutions of special education. Therefore, it is important to form the spirit of friendship, humanism, care and attention in the children's team. Prepare a child with disabilities for a trouble-free education in an inclusive school, create inclusive groups for children with mild disabilities and the opportunity for them to receive pre-school education. Demonstrate to the general public the humanity of the goals and principles of inclusive education and, most importantly, stand up for the rights of the child. It is obvious that in the life of the current pupils of the specialized boarding school No. 36 of the Kyzyltepa district with mental retardation, this was the first public recognition. Hilola Tokhtamurodova, a 3rd year student of the Tashkent Institute of Textile and Light Industry, the author of the "Peace with You" project, left with such an impression after meeting with rural children. As part of the first youth festival "IdeaFEST: from ideas to implementation", a participant from Uzbekistan won a grant from the main organizer in the amount of 12 thousand euros. In our country, "Peace be with you" started in December 2020. As part of the project, it is planned to visit all regions of the republic and conduct three-day trainings on manual creativity for children with Down syndrome and autism. The first workshops on quilling, stained glass, decoupage and ikebana were held in Gulistan, Jizzakh, Samarkand region with the participation of 85 children with Down syndrome and autism. Project participants in each region were awarded diplomas and colorful gifts. In the Navoi region, 25 pupils with disabilities from the Kyzyltepe boarding school were taught to work with papier-mâché and decoupage. Children studied with great interest and pleasure, did very beautiful work, and later admired and rejoiced at their work. Happiness and delight in their eyes delighted every member of the "Peace be with you" team.

"Perhaps we would have continued to live like this, knowing nothing about "sunny" children, if it were not for the will of the case that changed us and the world around us," says the author of the "Peace be with you" project Hilola Tokhtamurodova.

So, in 2017, a woman brought her 16-year-old daughter with Down syndrome to her, a teacher of needlework in one of the cultural centers. The girl's mother was very worried and wanted her child to be taught the craft. Hilola undertook to teach at home.

As it turned out, the girl really likes to draw. And with each lesson, she progressed, showing imagination, the ability to independently think over the drawing and decorate it to her liking. This circumstance inspired the young mentor to create a project aimed at developing creativity in children with Down syndrome and autism. After all, there are many examples when a person with such a diagnosis achieves success, creates a family, gets a profession and lives an ordinary happy life, like all healthy people. According to Н. Tokhtamurodova, the children - participants of the project - made her understand that life is a movement forward. You should not be disappointed and stop there. You need to study the world around you and people more deeply. Children is our future. So let's cherish, understand, develop them. And, most importantly, love!

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